

Mechanism of Copolymerisation of Styrene with Methyl Methacrylate in Presence of Zinc Chloride

A. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 13 September 1983, revised 22 August 1984, accepted 29 April 1985

Styrene and methyl methacrylate were copolymerised in the presence of azobisisobutyronitrile (initiator) and zinc chloride (complexing agent) at 50° for 2 h by employing dilatometry. Zinc chloride increased alternate placement of monomer units having same configuration in the polymer as shown by nmr spectroscopy. Zinc chloride does not act as chain transfer agent. These results suggest ternary molecular complex mechanism for the present system. The complex formation constant determined from proton chemical shift, is found to be 0.57 dm³ mol⁻¹.

COPOLYMERISATION of vinyl monomers in the presence of a Lewis acid may follow one of the three mechanisms, namely ternary molecular complex mechanism¹, cross propagation mechanism² and complex radical mechanism³. Kinetics⁴ of copolymerisation of methyl methacrylate with styrene in the presence of zinc chloride as complexing agent and azobisisobutyronitrile as initiator and the nmr⁵ study of the copolymers produced has already been reported. In the present paper the mechanism of the present system has been discussed.

Experimental

Styrene (sty) and methyl methacrylate (MMA) were purified according to the reported method⁶, and were stored under nitrogen atmosphere in the presence of silica gel. Benzene was washed with sulphuric acid and water, dried over calcium chloride and sodium wire, and distilled before use. The initiator azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was recrystallised twice from alcohol before use. Zinc chloride was used as such without further purification and was kept in a dessicator containing anhydrous calcium chloride.

The reaction was carried out in a modified dilatometric apparatus⁷. The MMA-ZnCl₂ complex was prepared according to the method given by Okuzawa⁸. The initiator (AIBN) was added to the complex. The complex and styrene were then injected to the dilatometer under nitrogen atmosphere and the reaction was carried out at 60° for 120 min. The progress of reaction was monitored with a cathetometer. The copolymer, precipitated with acidified methanol, was washed with acetonitrile and cyclohexane to remove the homopolymers.

The rate of copolymerisation (R_p) was calculated by equation (1) given by Srivastava⁴.

$$R_p \text{ (in mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) = 0.75150 \times 10^{-3} \times \frac{U}{t} \quad (1)$$

where, U is the percentage conversion of monomer per cm³ and t is the polymerisation time (in min).

The average degree of polymerisation ($\bar{p}_n$) was determined with the help of equation (2)⁹.

$$\eta_{int} = 5.76 \times 10^{-3} \times \bar{p}_n^{0.746} \quad (2)$$

where, η_{int} is the intrinsic viscosity of copolymer.

The average molecular weight of copolymer was determined with the formula,

$$\eta_{int} = KM^\alpha$$

where, M is the average molecular weight and K and α are constants whose values were taken as 13.2 × 10⁻⁵ and 0.71, respectively¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

When styrene and methyl methacrylate were copolymerised in the presence of azobisisobutyronitrile and zinc chloride (complexing agent), the rate of polymerisation was found to be a direct function of concentration of methyl methacrylate, azobisisobutyronitrile, zinc chloride, and inverse function of concentration of styrene, as reported earlier⁴. Zinc chloride increased the rate of propagation⁴. The effect of zinc chloride on viscosity average molecular weight ($\bar{M}_v$) of the polymer was studied by varying its concentration from 2 × 10⁻⁴ to 9 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ as shown in Table 1. The $\bar{M}_v$ was not affected by zinc chloride. This suggests that zinc chloride does not act as a chain transfer agent for the present system. The effect of zinc chloride on alternation regulation of monomer units in the polymer was studied with the help of nmr spectroscopy⁵. The value⁵ of σ (the probability of alternating MMA and sty units having the same configuration) increased from 0.860 to 0.871 when the concentration of zinc chloride was increased from 2 × 10⁻⁴ to 9 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. Therefore, it is clear that zinc

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ZINC CHLORIDE ON MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF POLYMER

Sl. no.	Concn. of zinc chloride $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm $^{-3}$	$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-3}$
1.	0	77.05
2.	2	80.05
3.	4	80.05
4.	6	78.57
5.	8	80.05
6.	9	80.76

chloride increased alternation regulation of monomer units in the polymer.

The above results suggest that this polymerization proceeds *via* formation of a ternary molecular complex, the structure of which was confirmed from the ir spectrum. The complex showed no charge transfer absorption bands in the range of 2777 to 3333 cm $^{-1}$. This suggests the following structure of the ternary molecular complex.

The value of equilibrium constant (k_a) for the formation of the ternary molecular complex, determined by using proton chemical shift of methyl methacrylate, was found to be 0.57 dm 3 mol $^{-1}$.

Therefore, on the basis of the above discussions the following mechanism may be proposed for the present system.

Mechanism :

Initiation step :

Propagation step :

Termination step :

References

1. N. G. GAYLORD and S. MATYSKA, *J. Macromol. Sci., Chem.*, 1970, 4, 1507.
2. S. YABUMOTO, K. ISHII and K. ARITA, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1969, 7, 1577.
3. M. HIROOKA, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Lett.*, 1972, 10, 171.
4. A. K. SRIVASTAVA and G. N. MATHUR, *Polymer*, 1981, 22, 391.
5. A. K. SRIVASTAVA and G. N. MATHUR, *Polymer*, 1982, 23, 20.
6. O. G. OVERBERGER and N. YAMAMOTO, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1966, 4, 3106.
7. A. K. SRIVASTAVA and G. N. MATHUR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 1118.
8. S. OKUZAWA, H. HIRAI and S. MIKISHIMA, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1969, 7, 1039.
9. H. HIRAI and M. KOMIYAMA, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1975, 13, 2419.
10. J. BRANDRUP, "Handbook of Polymer Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1966, p. IV-1.